

**SERVQUAL model Implementation to assist the Quality
of Education in early year setting in Abu Dhabi**

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Abstract

This research will the use of SERVQUAL model in early years in Abu Dhabi to enhance the level of education as well as the quality of the process. Considering the importance of early year setting in shaping the development of children, it is important to review the quality of education in early year setting. As children early year learning experience, the quality of teaching methods and the quality of the surrounding environment can have a significant impact on the children future life's, accordingly the quality of education programs is typically rated on two main dimensions.

1. Process
2. Structure

Process quality is measured and rated according to the level of interaction in the classroom, learning activities, learning materials, and the level of health and safety.

Structure as for learning setting structure, this is measured by adult to child ratio and the qualification level of teaching staff and training provided by the learning setting.

The purpose of this study was to determine the factors that influenced parents, teachers, stakeholder and Abu Dhabi Educational and knowledge satisfaction. A total of 64 parents, 12 teachers and concerned stakeholders agreed to take part in the survey in Ichiban Nurseries located in Abu Dhabi.

This study helps to examine the main objectives, methodologies, and findings of studies that have practiced the SERVQUAL model in preschools. This review helps to feed the research gap on preschools in the Gulf region quality of education with using technology as well as analyzing existing limited researches. According to factors affecting parents' satisfaction with the quality of preschool educational services study, it was found that Parents are satisfied with and willing to pay for the educational quality provided by preschool educational institutions. In addition, the quality of facilities, educational programs, financial costs, and support are all factors that influence parental satisfaction. Early years educational settings can benefit from this study because it adds to the body of knowledge and evidence available to them to help them improve and enhance their quality in order to increase parent satisfaction.

Keywords: Quality of education, SERVQUAL model, preschool settings, Survey, improvement

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Introduction

In the last decade and due to economic changes, the reliance on early year setting has raised dramatically. It has a vital role in shaping the characteristics and the level of education of young children as it also plays an important and fundamental role in the children academic success, social skills, emotional and physical development.

The aim of this study is to apply SERVQUAL model to assess the quality of education and overall wellbeing in early years.

The quality of education in early years covers various aspects, including the curriculum, teaching methods, learning environment, teacher-student interactions, and parental involvement. Evaluating and improving the quality of education in preschools is essential to ensure that children receive the best possible educational experiences during their early years.

SERVQUAL is a multidimensional well-validated research tool designed to measure service quality comprises five dimensions of service quality: reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles in order to provide a structured framework for evaluating the quality of services delivered to customers.

- Tangibles is the physical aspects of the provided service, equipment, and the personnel framework.
- Reliability is the capacity to provide the service as promised
- Responsiveness the ability to response to the customer and market needs in prompt and timely response.

- Assurance is to make sure that the service provider and the employees are skilled, respectful, and reliable.
- Empathy means showing care, personal attention, and understanding to customers.

SERVQUAL model is method to measure the quality of the service provided and the customer satisfaction. means showing care, personal attention, and understanding to customers. To identify any gaps or areas of improvement. By applying this model, educators and administrators can gain valuable insights into areas of strength and areas of development allowing them to make accurate decisions and build their strategies to enhance the quality of education. Furthermore, we will identify the research problem, objectives, methodology, and findings of studies that have deployed by the SERVQUAL model in early year settings.

Literature Review

In The early years education to sustain quality is a challenge. SERVQUAL model is one of the methodologies to assess the quality established by Parasurman, Zeithaml, and Berry in the late 1980s. SERVQUAL's model it's not complicated however its effective, where quality can measure approach is simple and straightforward but successful: quality can be measured not only through assess the service provided but also through identifying the gap between customer expectation and what is service received. This model contains five main factors: tangibles, assurance, responsiveness, empathy, and reliability to highlight the identified gap. The concept was started first in the business sector, eventually the model achieved improvements in the education sector when the service provider realized that parents and student concede act exactly like to service clients, holding assumptions that influenced their sense of satisfaction and trust.

Educational studies started applying SERVQUAL to assess quality in school, universities, and training schools eventually the model became integrated in the field of education study. These early academic studies shaped an efficient framework for service quality highlighted the strengths and limitations of organizations that inspection findings. The researchers in Turkey, Malaysia, south Korea and Europe applied the method to parental expectations, educator's performance, organizational credibility, and student's satisfaction. The five factors of the SERVQUAL model reflect effectively of educational and learning environment, in particular, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, which usually effect the choice of parents and student when selecting the school.

When researcher adapted the SERVQUAL model in early years setting the model demonstrate a strong adaptability showing that it can effectively evaluate the quality of education. Worldwide researcher from Malaysia, Vietnam, Finland and other Asian regions illustrates that parents tend to assess the quality of the settings using the five dimensions of the SERVQUAL model. Parents seeking for a setting where the staff are skilled and professional, the promote response to their concern, reliable daily routine and understanding their needs. The tangible factor from classrooms, facilities and other educational equipment act as baseline for parent's expectation rather than influencing factor. However early years educations studies indicate that there is a significant relationship between children wellbeing and parent's quality expectations: see the education service better when they feel their children happy, safe, engaged and comfortable.

The literature that apply SERVQUAL model for continues validity. And this will provide the policies maker opportunity to enhance quality and improve the service by providing a clear method to identify the gap. This approach also highlights the parent's expectations in early years setting, these expectations vary according to influencing factors such as previous experience, cultural norms and their perspective for children development. Above all, SERVQUAL model enable the early year setting to understand how the quality of service influence by the loyalty of parents, word of mouth and the parents willing to enrol their children.

Furthermore, the literature also highlights a major weakness. SERVQUAL model can be impacted by Social attractiveness, emotions, or the unwillingness of parents to criticize their own opinions. Although the widespread use of the model the complexity neuter of the early year education from the teaching methods that parents could not fully understand, different curriculum and the children development milestone cannot be fully represented by the five dimensions of the mode. Updating the items makes the model more important, but also makes the cross-study analyses and evaluating challenging. Another challenge is that SERVQUAL captures a "snapshot" instead of long-term adjustments, it does not always reflect who perception change when children grow up. Researcher also highlighted the imbalance between the parent's evaluations and the expert evaluations; parents usually assess the quality over educators do, addressing the question of whether SERVQUAL evaluate accurate educational quality or simply satisfaction of parents.

This current literature supported in identifying the particular research gaps that this research will be addressing. There are very limited researches applying SERVQUAL to early years settings in Abu Dhabi, even though early years programs in the UAE are growing rapidly and parents' expectations are growing as well. Particularly, there is an absence of research that study parental attitude within multicultural early years contexts such as this research, where are families coming from diverse backgrounds with different expectations. Furthermore, there is a gap in connecting SERVQUAL outcomes with the day to day educators' practices in the real-world environment. Through this research, the aim was to highlight this gap by applying the SERVQUAL model directly to an early year setting in Abu Dhabi, analyzing and evaluating the gaps that are important for most of the parents, and connecting these outcomes to practical recommendations to enhance the quality by improving the communication and satisfaction of parent. The research objective is not only evaluating perceptions, but to add a deeper comprehending of how quality service framework can help and support early years education in the UAE.

Research challenges/Question/Objective

Considering early years education is essential in the early development of children, ensuring high-quality educational experiences can be challenging keeping in mind the age targeted in this research, in addition the sample size due low rate of responses from all parents and teachers which might affect generalizability as the research targeted parents and teachers from Ichiban Nursery in Abu Dhabi. Using a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, the recommended sample size for the total 135 parents is approximately 100 participants. However, for early childhood settings, a response range between 50 and 70 parent participants is considered sufficient for descriptive SERVQUAL studies and due to high proportion of working parents the response rate was limited. As well as the response bias due to the cultural sensitivities as UAE culture might hesitate to give negative feedback or if the parents or teachers fill the survey quickly without understanding the questions.

The research aims to address the following questions:

1. What are the factors that determine in building the quality of education in early year setting?
2. How to measure the quality of service in preschool using SERVQUAL model?
3. What are the challenges we may face while applying SERVQUAL model in preschools?

4. How can the results of implementing the SERVQUAL model be used to build strategies to enhance the quality in the early year setting?

By highlighting the challenges and research questions, this review aims to present an understanding in the assessment and enhancement of the quality of education in early year setting and eventually develop the policies, procedures, strategies and practices that enhance the overall educational experiences of young children in early year settings.

The main research objectives of this study are:

1. To identify the key dimensions and indicators of service quality in early year education: This objective involves examining the specific factors that contribute to the quality of education in early year settings. By identifying these dimensions and indicators, the study aims to provide a comprehensive structure for evaluating the quality of educational services provided to young children.
2. To utilize the SERVQUAL model to assess the quality of education in early year setting: This objective focuses on the implementation of the SERVQUAL model in early year settings. By using this model, the study aims to evaluate the level of service quality provided to children, parents, teacher, Government, and other stakeholders in the early years settings environment. It aims to measure the perceived performance of the early year setting according to the stakeholders' expectations.
3. To analyze the findings and their implications of applying the SERVQUAL model in early year setting: This objective includes analyzing the results obtained from using the SERVQUAL model to assess the quality of education. The study aims to analyze the gaps between perceived service quality and expected service quality, and to identify the area of strengths and improvements. understandings the implications of the findings that will enhance the overall quality of education in the early year setting.
4. To explore the challenges and limitations of using the SERVQUAL model in early years education: This objective aims to investigate the potential difficulties and limitations associated with applying the SERVQUAL model in the context of early years. It aims to identify the barriers and constraints that may delay the effective implementation of the model and provide recommendations to overcome these challenges.
5. To recommend strategies for enhancing the quality of education in early years settings: Based on the research findings and understandings, this objective aims to develop practical recommendations and strategies for improving the quality of education in early year setting. It aims to provide evidence-based approaches that can be

implemented by educators, administrators, and other stakeholders to improve the educational experiences and outcomes of young children in early years settings.

By achieving these objectives, this research will contribute to the existing knowledge and understanding of assessing and improving the quality of education in early years settings using the SERVQUAL model.

Methodology Used

Research design and setting:

This research was quantitative, descriptive research design. A comprehensive literature Review was conducted to gather insights into the implementation of the SERVQUAL model in early years education. Relevant research articles and scholarly publications were examined to understand the key dimensions, indicators, and methodologies used in assessing service quality in early year settings. This literature review formed the foundation for developing the research context. *New studies, for instance Emre et al. (2023), have implemented the SERVQUAL model to evaluate service quality in preschools in Turkey, emphasizing the role of empathy and assurance in parent satisfaction. Their findings align with the growing global interest in adapting service quality frameworks to early childhood education, though cultural and structural differences for example teacher-child ratios and curriculum standards It might end in different priorities for various regions.*

Research population and data collection

Primary data was collected to carried out the assessment of quality of education in early years using the SERVQUAL model. E-Surveys were designed to capture the views and expectations among stakeholders including parents and teachers through Google forms link the survey took place for one week to ensure largest possible sample. Government feedback was collected from Abu Dhabi Department of Education and knowledge after their education evaluation visit as three strengths and three area for improvement provided to the setting. And in-person interview with owner was conducted. The survey questions were developed based on the dimensions and indicators identified in the literature review. Ethical principles were considered throughout the research as the survey was anonymous, volunteered, parents and teacher informed that the data will be used for a research purpose, formal consent provided for parents, teacher and Ichiban Nursery to pe part of the research. Clear communication was established to inform all parties about their right to withdraw of the research study at any time. Confidentiality to maintain and analyses data were taken throughout the research.

Data Analysis and measurement

The collected data was analyzed using statistical techniques and qualitative analysis methods. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the survey responses and calculate mean scores,

percentage, and other relevant measures. The parents survey was designed to include 15 questions five questions covered the sample demographic and the remaining 10 questions covered the SERVQUAL model five dimensions: reliability (2 items), responsiveness (2 items), assurance (2 items), empathy (2 items), and tangibles (2 items). "The Survey questions are included in appendix B" Teacher survey was included 13 questions the first 3 items addressed teacher demographic and same as the parents survey the other 10 questions 2 items for each factor of SERVQUAL model. "The Survey questions are included in appendix C" Gap analysis was conducted to compare the perceived performance and expected performance in each dimension of service quality. Qualitative data from three open-ended questions throughout a semi-structured interview lasted for 10 minutes with the Ichiban owner were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring themes and patterns. "The interview questions are included appendix D".

1. Findings Interpretation: The findings from the data analysis were interpreted and discussed in the context of the research objectives. The identified gaps between perceived and expected service quality were analyzed to identify areas of strength and areas requiring improvement. The research findings were compared and contrasted with previous studies and existing literature to provide a comprehensive understanding of the quality of education in preschools and the applicability of the SERVQUAL model.
2. Recommendations and Conclusion: Based on the research findings, practical recommendations and strategies were formulated to enhance the quality of education in preschool settings. These recommendations were derived from the analysis of the gaps in service quality and the identified areas for improvement. The conclusion section summarized the main findings, discussed their implications, and highlighted the contributions of the study.

By implementing this methodology, the study aimed to gather empirical data, analyze the quality of education in early years setting using the SERVQUAL model, and provide evidence-based recommendations for enhancing the overall educational experiences of young children in early year settings.

[Project Discussion/Facts](#)

Data was collected from multiple stakeholders, including parents, teachers, owner and government through surveys and interviews. The survey questions were designed to measure the perceptions and expectations related to various dimensions of service quality, such as reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles. A total of 64 participants 58 mothers and 6 father, 27 children were (3-4) years old, 25 children were (2-3) years old, 8 children (1-2) year-old 3 children less than one year old. 60.9% of the children were male and

39.1% were female. 54.7% of the children were enrolled for more than one year were. While a 12 teacher were involved in the data collection process 41.7% working for (3-5) years in Ichiban Nursery, 33.3 % more than 5 years, 25% working (1-3) years, 75% bachelor qualified, 16.7% diploma qualified, 8.3% post graduate. The feedback from ADEK was three strengths which are connection between practitioners and children, the trust with families and a purposeful environment indoors and outdoors. While the areas of improvement were incorporating Emirati games as well as displaying more of children's work throughout the setting.

The survey results revealed valuable insights into the current state of service quality in early year setting. The overall satisfaction levels were found to be high from both perspective parents and teacher, with some variations across different dimensions. The highest-rated dimension was tangible responsiveness, reliability and assurance, indicating that parents, teachers, which also align with ADEK observations about the capabilities of the early year staff and their ability to provide a safe and secure learning environment and the parents trust. However, the dimension of empathy, which measures willingness to support and understand from management, received moderate level from teacher perspective indicating areas of improvement identified through the survey. The dimension of tangible, includes physical facilities and resources scored higher than other dimensions. Similar to Emre et al. (2023), who identified empathy and assurance as critical drivers of parent satisfaction in Turkish preschools, this study found high parent ratings for assurance (96%) and empathy (90-93%) in Abu Dhabi. However, while Emre et al. reported challenges in reliability (e.g., inconsistent service delivery), the present study highlighted tangibles as the highest factor rated (96%-97%) satisfactions from parents and 100% from teachers. However, empathy from teacher perspective was moderate (58%-74%). Suggesting that regional infrastructure and economic standing may shape SERVQUAL outcomes the above finding will Shows SERVQUAL's relevance beyond Western/Asian societies.

The analysis of the survey results shed light on the gaps between perceived service quality and expected service quality in early years education. These gaps provide opportunities for improvement and serve as a basis for developing strategies to enhance the quality of education. The findings emphasized the importance of addressing empathy in early years settings to create a supportive and engaging learning environment for the educators. Even though satisfaction level were high, there are always areas for improvement to sustain and to align with the international early year's standards. The recommendations were created. First, enhancing communication channels and establishing regular feedback mechanisms between management

and teachers can improve empathy. This can include one to one meeting. Second, implementing professional development programs for teachers to enhance their empathy, skills can contribute to better understanding and meeting the individual needs of Staff. Providing ongoing training and support for teachers can promote a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. Furthermore, the analysis highlighted the significance of continuous evaluation and improvement in early years settings. Regular assessments of service quality, using tools like the SERVQUAL model, can help monitor progress and identify areas for further enhancement. It is essential to involve all stakeholders in the quality improvement process, including parents, teachers, administrators, government and even the children themselves. Collaborative efforts and a shared commitment to providing high-quality education are crucial for achieving the desired outcomes.

Another finding was noticed from the research is a clear positive relationship between the duration of enrollment and the parent’s level of satisfactions across several dimensions of the SERVQUAL model. Parents who their children enrolled for more than one year score a higher level of satisfaction regarding the ability of the early years setting to adhere to the educational program and accommodating the parent’s needs. suggesting that the more years of enrollment the more trust built between parents and the early year setting.

In conclusion, the project's findings and analysis underscored the value of implementing the SERVQUAL model in preschool settings to assess and improve the quality of education. The identified gaps in service quality provided insights into areas requiring attention and interventions. By implementing the recommended strategies, early years setting can enhance empathy, and overall service quality, ultimately providing young learners with a positive and enriching educational experience.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research explored the application of the SERVQUAL model in assessing the quality of education in early years settings. Through a comprehensive analysis of survey data

collected from parents and teachers, valuable insights were obtained regarding the perceived service quality and expectations in early years setting education. The findings of the research indicated that while there were strengths in certain dimensions such as assurance and tangibles, there were also area for improvement, particularly in empathy. The results emphasized the importance of effective communication and prompt support in creating a high-quality learning environment for early years settings.

By utilizing the SERVQUAL model as a framework for evaluation, this study has provided valuable insights into the gaps between perceived service quality and expected service quality in early years setting education. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the factors that influence the quality of education in early years settings and provide a basis for developing strategies to enhance the overall educational experience.

Based on the analysis, several recommendations have been proposed. Enhancing communication channels, establishing regular feedback mechanisms, and implementing professional development programs for teachers can address the identified gaps in empathy. Furthermore, continuous evaluation and improvement processes, involving all stakeholders, are crucial for maintaining and enhancing the quality of education in early years setting.

The findings of this study have practical implications for educators, administrators, and policymakers in the field of early childhood education. By implementing the recommended strategies and addressing the identified gaps, early years setting can create a nurturing and supportive environment that fosters the holistic development of young children.

Overall, this study has contributed to the existing literature on quality in early years education by applying the SERVQUAL model. It has shed light on the dimensions of service quality that are particularly important in the context of preschools and provided insights into areas requiring attention and improvement. The study highlights the significance of ongoing evaluation, collaboration, and continuous improvement efforts in ensuring the delivery of high-quality education to preschoolers.

In conclusion, this research serves as a valuable resource for educators, researchers, and policymakers aiming to enhance the quality of education in preschool settings. By employing the SERVQUAL model and implementing the recommended strategies, stakeholders can work together to create a positive and enriching educational experience for young children, laying a strong foundation for their future development and success.

[Appendix](#)

Appendix A

This Appendix refer references present in our project

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Appendix B

This Appendix refer to the Parents survey questions and figures

Respondent Relationship:

64 responses

Child's age

64 responses

Child's Gender:

64 responses

Duration of Enrollment:

64 responses

- Less than one year
- More than one year

Program Type

62 responses

- Full day
- Part day

البيئة نظيفة ومجهزة بشكل جيد. The environment is clean and well-equipped.

64 responses

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

المواد التعليمية والألعاب مناسبة لعمر الأطفال. Learning materials and toys are age-appropriate and good quality.
64 responses

الروضة تلتزم بالبرنامج التعليمي المعطى. The preschool follows the educational program shared with parents.
63 responses

يتم متابعة تطور طفلي بانتظام. My child's development is monitored consistently.
64 responses

My inquiries are answered promptly.
يتم الرد على استفساراتي بسرعة.
64 responses

Issues or concerns are addressed quickly.
يتم حل المشكلات أو الملاحظات بسرعة .
64 responses

I feel my child is in a safe environment.
أشعر أن طفلي في مكان آمن.
64 responses

المعلمات ذوات خبرة وكفاءة. Teachers are knowledgeable and competent.
64 responses

يتم التعامل مع طفلي باهتمام فردي. My child receives individual attention.
64 responses

الروضة تفهم احتياجات الأسرة. The preschool understands and accommodates family needs.
63 responses

Appendix C

This Appendix refer to the teachers' survey questions and figures

Years of Experience

12 responses

Education qualification

12 responses

Years at Ichiban

12 responses

Learning materials are sufficient

11 responses

Classroom environment supports learning.

12 responses

Management provides clear plans.

12 responses

The curriculum is applied consistently.

12 responses

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

I receive quick support when needed.

12 responses

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Feedback is taken seriously.

12 responses

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

I feel safe at work.

12 responses

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

I receive enough training.

12 responses

- Yes
- No

Management understands my needs.

12 responses

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

My time and circumstances are respected.

12 responses

Appendix D

This Appendix refer to the interview conducted with the owner

Stakeholder interview: the question was what can enhance the quality of education in Ichiban. What strategies or initiatives do you believe can contribute to improving the quality of education in Ichiban Comparing now from when you started your business?

“By keeping old values intact and trying to avoid exposure of AI and technology and to enhance their interpersonal and intrapersonal skills by staging a hands-on platform. In addition, ensuring parents are made aware of the seriousness of the extremely vital years and stages of development in their child’s life. Continuously educating parents on the wellbeing of children”

Appendix E

This Appendix refer to the program used in the research

1. Googol form
2. Excel